

ADVANTAGES OF USING COMMUNICATIVE TRAINING IN PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR PROFESSIONAL- COMMUNICATIVE ACTIVITY

¹X.I.Ibraimov, ²O.I.Yadgarova

¹Director of the Scientific Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences of Uzbekistan named after T.N.Kori Niyozzi. Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

²PhD, Associated Professor, Samarkand state foreign languages institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10364327>

Abstract: *This article discusses the advantages of interactive seminars, interesting and non-standard educational and extracurricular activities, as well as the advantages of using communicative training in preparing future teachers for professional communicative activities. Examples of effective language learning schemes and communicative training exercises through the organization of communicative trainings are also given.*

Keywords: *communication, training, competence, information transfer, coding, discussion, teacher.*

The state policy aimed at achieving a specific goal in the field of education of our country is recognized as one of the priority directions of the development of social society. "Priority tasks for the radical improvement of the education system are defined, including the development of a targeted program for improving the education system in schools, bringing the knowledge and skills of pedagogues to the international level, and entering the international ratings of higher education institutions by QS and TNE Tasks such as [2] are defined, to educate young people, to develop their speaking skills, to train future teachers as specialists who fully meet world standards in teaching them to communicate, to form their professional-communicative competence. , it is important to scientifically substantiate the mechanisms of development of competences for demonstrating creative potential and pedagogical skills. Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev on October 8, 2019 No. PD-5847 "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" was adopted. The main goal of the decree is to define the priorities of the systematic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, to raise the process of training of independent thinking highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high moral and ethical qualities to a new level in terms of quality, higher education modernization of education, development of social sphere and economic sectors based on advanced educational technologies [1]. Such urgency in the field of education requires the development of scientifically based proposals and recommendations for the development of professional and communicative competence of future teachers.

For successful communication, a person must possess two main directions of communication: external and internal, i.e. first, a person must learn to understand himself, listen to himself, negotiate with himself, manage himself, then - he needs to establish contact with other people. Therefore, communicative training is, first of all, psychological, and secondly, technological.

Communicative training literally means "common" or "used by all". Communication usually means communication, transfer of information from person to person, a specific form of interaction between people during their activities. In practical terms, it is a process of exchange of ideas and information between two or more people that leads to mutual understanding [3].

The main goal of communicative training is to introduce an effective mechanism of information perception and understanding, encoding, transmission and exchange into human activity.

There are four main components of information sharing.

- Sender, person who creates information and transmits it.
- The message, information itself, coded and transmitted using language symbols.
- Communication tools.
- Receiver, the person to whom the information is intended and who interprets and understands it.

The stages of organizing communicative training are listed in the table below.

1. Origin of the idea.	2. Selection of encoding and direction.	3. Transfer.	4. Coding
<p>What kind of meaningful idea or message does the sender want to convey. Unfortunately, many contact attempts fail at this first stage because the sender doesn't spend enough time thinking about the idea.</p>	<p>Before conveying an idea, the sender must use symbols to encode it, using words, intonation, and gestures. This encoding turns an idea into a message. Effective coding requires an understanding of verbal and non-verbal communication languages, and an understanding of creativity and unconscious processes.</p>	<p>In the third step, the sender uses the channel to deliver the message to the receiver. Communication can be verbal, written, or through sight or touch, and you can deliver a message through communication or live streaming. It's about the physical transmission of the message, which many mistake for the process of communication itself.</p>	<p>After the sender sends the message, the receiver decodes it. Decoding is the translation of the sender's symbols into the receiver's thoughts. If the symbols chosen by the sender have exactly the same meaning for the receiver, the latter will know exactly what the sender had in mind when he formed his idea. If no response to the idea is required, the exchange of information should end there or continue with comments.</p>

Also, during communicative training sessions, work is carried out at each stage of these elements.

1. The entire communication system, complex relationships between people, communication management system is implemented.

2. Students know themselves, their characteristics, strengths and weaknesses, understand the specific features of perception, encode information.

3. Develops self-presentation and speaking skills in students.

4. Develops skills in effective creation of verbal and non-verbal messages.

5. Means of information delivery and their characteristics are studied for the ability to choose appropriate means in a given situation.

6. Develops the ability to understand other people, to predict the reasons for their behavior and to understand, listen and hear.

7. Develops feedback skills.

In communicative training sessions, participants are taught the technologies of effective performance of all communication functions.

"Thus, communicative training has the following content:

* psychology of communication, including self-knowledge, understanding of other people;

* communication management technologies: management and planning of communication, as well as development of a personal communication plan, self-presentation, monitoring, assessment of communication effectiveness, etc.

* organizing an effective communication process (psychologically and technologically);

* understanding the laws of giving and transmitting information, obtaining it, separating one's own equipment" [7];

• formation and strengthening of trust and sympathy, management of emotions;

• communication techniques in different situations.

Results of effective mastering of communication technologies for participants:

Theoretical knowledge serves as a bridge in mastering any subject. This shows that practical training is very important.[5]

Today, it is difficult to imagine pedagogical activity without communicative methods, because the only goal of learning the basics of any subject is to develop a mature specialist. From this point of view, communication is carried out by the speakers through various statements. In such cases, the teacher should not judge students' opinions as wrong, on the contrary, as much as possible, he should help students, encourage them, encourage them not to be afraid to express wrong opinions, and finally he should analyze each of the expressed opinions.

Figure 2.2. An effective language learning scheme through the organization of communicative training.

One of the most important requirements for the educational system is to teach independent thinking. Today, the following communicative training exercises are available for future teachers based on the experience of pedagogues in the USA and Great Britain [6]:

"**Creative problem solving**" - to use this method, the beginning of the story is read and students are asked to decide how to end it;

"**Quick answers**" help to increase the efficiency of the lesson;

"**Warm up**" exercises use various classroom games to engage students in the lesson;

"**Pantomime**" - this method can be used when a student is tired of doing a lesson or writing exercises that require the explanation of very complex topics;

The "**Chain History**" method predicts that students will speak, contributes to improving and strengthening memory;

"**Role-playing games**". This method can be used in all types of lessons. Professionals such as translators, writers and poets can participate in the course and communicate with students;

"**Gathering of Scientists**". In this way, you can "invite" such poets and writers as W.Shakespeare, A.Navoi, R.Burns. In such moments, using the words of wisdom said in the classroom will help young men and women to become perfect people;

The method "**When pictures speak**" is more convenient, helps to develop students' oral speech in teaching English, which requires the use of thematic pictures;

"**Quiz cards**" are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to attend classes at the same time, which saves time.

"**Creative problem solving**" method, the beginning of the story is read and the students' judgment is referred to how it will end;

"**Quick answers**" help to improve the effectiveness of the lesson.

In conclusion, it should be said that the current situation in psychological training, the use of interactive methods and practical tasks during the training leave a great impression on the training participants. The social and emotional state of society consists of three main components: the moral compatibility of students, their social aspirations and moral education. These

components relate to the most subtle aspects of human behavior, intelligence, will and emotions, and in many ways help a person's use, creative activity, cooperation with others and cohesiveness. When communicative trainings are used, it is observed that the working ability of the student team increases, the level of resolution of conflict situations becomes easier, the stress resistance of students increases, the effectiveness of the communication process increases, and the quality of preparation for professional activity increases.

REFERENCES

1. <https://lex.uz/docs/4545884> O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 08.10.2019 yildagi PF-5847-sonli “O‘zbekiston Respublikasi oliy ta’lim tizimini 2030 yilgacha rivojlantirish Konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida”gi Farmoni, – Qonun hujjatlari ma’lumotlari milliy bazasi, 09.10.2019 y., 06/19/5847/3887-son.
2. <https://lex.uz/docs/5841063> O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 28.01.2022 yildagi PF-60-sonli “2022 — 2026 yillarga mo‘ljallangan Yangi O‘zbekistonning Taraqqiyot strategiyasi to‘g‘risida”gi farmoni.– Qonunchilik ma’lumotlari milliy bazasi, 29.01.2022 y., 06/22/60/0082-son, 18.03.2022 y., 06/22/89/0227-son, 21.04.2022 y.
3. Мальханова.И. А. "Коммуникативный тренинг."//Ж. (2006): 160-160.
4. Ибраимов Х. И. Коммуникативная компетентность как механизм профессионального саморазвития будущего педагога //Ж.Проблемы педагогики. – 2018. – №. 2 (34).-78-с.
5. O.I.Yadgarova. Bo‘lajak o‘qituvchilarni professional-kommunikativ kompetentligini rivojlantirishda psixologik treninglardan foydalanish imkoniyatlari. Monografiya. – Samarqand: “Samarqand davlat chet tillar instituti” nashriyoti, 2023. – 110 bet.
6. Ibragimovich Kh.I. Peculiarities of using credit-module technologies in the higher education system of Uzbekistan //Integration of science, education and practice. Scientific-methodical journal. - 2021. - P. 209-214.
7. Ibraimov Kh. "Theoretical and methodological basis of quality control and evaluation of education in higher education system." International journal of discourse on innovation, integration and education 1 (2020): 6-15.
8. Ibragimov, X., Abdullayeva Sh. "Pedagogika nazariyasi (darslik)." T.: Fan va texnologiya 288 (2008).
9. Ibraimov X.I., M.Quronov. Umumiy pedagogika (darslik). –T., “Shaffof”, 2023, 416-bet.
10. Ibragimovich I. K. et al. PEDAGOGICAL ABILITIES OF A TEACHER, STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT //湖南大学学报 (自然科学版). – 2021. – Т. 48. – №. 12.
11. Ибрагимов Х. И. ПЕДАГОГИКА И ВОСПИТАНИЕ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 1-1 (80). – С. 608-611.
12. Ibragimovich, Ibraimov Kholboy. "Intensive methods of teaching foreign languages at university." Вопросы науки и образования 27 (39) (2018): 78-80.
13. Ибраимов Х. И. Педагогические и психологические особенности обучения взрослых //Academy. – 2019. – №. 10 (49). – С. 39-41.
14. Ибрагимов Х. И. Организация самостоятельной работы студентов в условиях цифровизации вузовского образования //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2020. – №. 7 (54). – С. 74-75.
15. https://www.magisterjournal.ru/docs/VM108_2.pdf
16. <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=22877941>

